

Review Article

A political economic analysis on the development of Chinese film industry from 1994 to 2017

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Abstract: *In 1994, the Chinese film industry was opened to the world. The government transformed the most important propaganda means of the Party into a commercial culture industry. Though, the state still controls the industry by using cultural protective policies to not only protect domestic industries but also protect the distinctive nature of the culture from global intervention. Nevertheless, as an unexpected case in the globalization aftermath, the Chinese film industry not only wins over the imported movies in the domestic film market but also the second-largest film market in the world. Accordingly, the thesis examines the elements that contribute to this such incredible success. Locating the Chinese film industry in the world within globalization, this thesis discusses the following research questions: What are the elements that help the Chinese film industry in achieving its success? To answer the question, there are three sub research questions that the paper would study in each chapter of the paper. Did the protectionist policy helps to develop the Chinese film industry under the influence of Hollywood movies? What are the characters of Chinese blockbusters? What are the contributions of the market's factors according to Litman's model that help the Chinese film market share surpass Hollywood movies? By using a historical-political analyzing method to approach the research question, the thesis was organized as 3 main chapters. The findings are found by conducting an in-depth analysis of China's film policies based upon reliable data incorporating with a historical perspective. Popular protective policies such as quota policies, screen policies, subsidies contribute to supporting the film domestic market to have space to develop while the censorship was the only policy that effectively helps protect the domestic culture from Hollywood's influence. Analyzing the success of the movie "The Wolf Warrior 2" reveals "Chinese patriotism with Hollywood characteristics" which could be the new theme for Chinese blockbuster to develop in the future. The contribution of private corporations in the industry still limited to the exhibition market. Broaden the presence of private companies in other aspects such as production and distribution would help the Chinese film market stronger and more integrated, which is important to stand out in the world film market.*

Keywords: Chinese film industry, cultural policies, globalization, Chinese blockbusters, Hollywood characteristics.

Introduction

Along the Chinese film history, the Chinese film market was completely restricted under the control of the People's Republic of China (Hao & Chen, 2010). Due to the wars and national education purpose, the government had kept the market closed until 1994. In 1994, to save the market from constantly declining, China made a necessary but difficult choice to open up its cinema market to foreign competition. Foreign films had been imported by the government before. Though those films were imported to serve the political purpose instead of commercial purpose. When opening the market, China still kept the power to restrict the number of imported films at the number of 10 films (Yeh and Davis, 2008). Imported foreign movies helped domestic cinemas to keep some of the box office earnings through revenue-sharing policy (Su, 2014). Considering that China has the world's largest population, the entire box-office takings for 1994 were a very small amount, only 1.73 billion RMB. Moreover, the Chinese studios in total produced 146 feature films, imported foreign movies were only 10. However, the share for domestically produced films was only 20 percent (He, 2012). After the introduction of Hollywood films on the Chinese box office market, the market share of domestically produced films declined dramatically to a low record. Nevertheless, in 2004, the first time in 10 years, after opening up the market, domestically produced films accounted for 55% of the market (He, 2012). In 2014, 20 years after opening up the market, the size of the market had grown nearly 20 times up to 33.6 billion RMB compared to the same figure in 2004. The number of domestic produced films also increased 4 times up to 618 features in 2014 (Chinese Film Publication, 2018). In 2018, the Chinese film industry has appeared as a new star in international film market when become the second biggest industry in the world (Associated Press, 2018). The world has witnessed a remarkable increase in the Chinese film industry only in two decades, which makes the industry a valuable case to study.

The starting point of studying an industry is to study the market structure according to the Industrial Organization model proposed by scholars B.R. Litman (Litman, 1998). The market performance of an industry is influenced by market conduct; the market conduct then is influenced by market structure. The market structure includes institutional factors that affect the development of an industry such as the government, overall nature of the industry and the type of the product. The thesis hence in the process of analyzing the development of the Chinese film industry would study the influence of the government's policy and the general nature of the industry. The Chinese film industry is one of the cultural products that heavily under the control of the government

historically. The influence of the Chinese government's influence is more considered when the country decided to open to the world. More than that, in the era of globalization, the introduction of cultural trade into international free trade regimes have been arising the issues in restricting the power of individual nations to exercise cultural protections due to the contradiction between protecting the culture and pursuing greater economic integration. Specifically, from an economic perspective, governments need to decide to choose to favor the domestic producers or customer's benefits by opening freely the market to the world. Or should the governments choose to protect their domestic cultures? China, in the flow, has decided to open its film market to the world but still keep its control over the industry, which makes the influence of the government's policies noticeably important to the research.

Historically, in the film industry, the conflict between the two ideologies, free trade market and cultural protectionism could be traced to the dominance of Hollywood as a world film leader after World War I when about 90 percent of the world film screens were dominated by U.S. films in 1926 (Segrave, 1997). The governments from others countries started the protection policy with the aim of protecting domestic film industries in the increasing penetration of Hollywood films from the U.S. However, not long later, after World War II, the U.S. government has an increasing commitment to free trade. In the 1960s and 1970s, under the slogan of "free flow of information", the open market campaign in the communication field encountered the most heated debate and resistance in the third world nations who called for a New World Information and Communication Order (NWICO) (Herman and McChesney, 1997). In the 1970s and 1980s, the fear of the third world over American hegemony and cultural imperialism increased due to the findings of Nordenstreng and Varis in 1974 about the one-way flow of television and feature film programs from the U.S. to the rest of the world. The U.S. government along the 1980s and 1990s increased policies globally of liberalizing trade ideology and opening export markets campaign (Destler, 2016). The world then witnessed a rapid trend of trade liberalization, privatization, and commercialization through the multilateral and bilateral trade negotiations that led by the U.S. and other countries such as General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), the World Trade Organization (WTO),...(Hufbauer & Warren, 1999).

The result of this media liberalization process was the dominance of U.S. films in domestic markets in other nations. Many film industries were under crisis. Domestic share in most European

countries was under 20 percent (Segrave, 1997). In Korea, opening foreign direct distribution made the domestic share fell from 50 percent to less than 40 percent in the 1990s and 80 percent of box office revenues went to the U.S. films in 1988 (Segrave, 1997). A huge flow of U.S. investment and productions of Hollywood styled films in Canada when it opened the market for foreign investment in film production. Mexico's productions fell from 100 to 4 films per year after the abolishing of its screen quota in 1994. In Germany, Britain, France, Spain, Turkey, and other countries shared similar situations. Moreover, in that period of time, in the U.S. the market share of foreign films had also declined dramatically from 10 percent in the 1960s to 7 percent in 1986 to less than 2 percent in 1991, and 1/3 of 1 percent in 2005 (Marvasti & Canterbury, 2005). The competitive advantages of Hollywood movies mainly came from deregulation and technological innovation (Wasko, 1994). And the trend of Hollywood's increasing domination obviously has kept continuing for a long period of time. Under the circumstance of the increase in trade liberalization, it is worthy to note that the resistance to the American film dominance has never stopped since the Cultural Protection Movement originated in Europe in the 1920s. Many countries request exceptions in protecting domestic cultural goods and services due to its identity value and meanings. In 1947, Article IV of the GATT agreements, Special Provisions Relating to Cinematograph Films, allowed using screen quotas to reserve screen times for locally produced films (Marvasti & Canterbury, 2005). And in the fall of 1993 when the North America Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) and GATT negotiations were concluded with cultural exclusions became the focal point of the negotiations, the Cultural of resistance culminated (McAnany & Wilkinson, 1996). Since then, cultural policies became a popular tools that nations use to protect their film domestic market despite the argument about its effectiveness by scholars.

The film industry of the People's Republic of China since the 1950s with national subsidies, central planning, and tight management of output and exhibition, has demonstrated a radical cinema in both content and industrial structure. Following a socialist ideology, the Chinese film industry under the lead of the government was permeated with convictions of party-state sovereignty and national authenticity. When the socialist system was riddled with inefficiency and mismanagement in the 1980s, this state-backed radical cinema crumbled. With the intention to save the Chinese economy from complete collapse, the "Reform and opening" policy was announced in 1978, which transformed the market from centrally planned economy into a largely market orientation (Chu, 2010). The Chinese film industry, like other industries in the 1980s and

1990s, experienced a series of straining structural reforms, transforming gradually to a market-oriented, profit-driven enterprise from a state propaganda apparatus. The Communist Party switched to a quasi-capitalist system and accepted the market economy as the correct path to China's new life. However, for a long time, the media has played as a crucial role in maintaining the one-party socialist state, marketization in the film industry was designed to remain in the hand of the state. As in Russia and Eastern Europe, with some trepidation, China chose to introduce market mechanisms to its state-owned enterprises (SOEs) which were converted into shareholding corporations instead of completely privatizing its economy (Larus, 2005). The corporatization of SOEs allows the state to gain a crucial foothold in the globalized market. The Chinese film marketization under these actions was differentiated from the industry in capitalist economies, which famous for the name of "socialist market economy" or a market economy with Chinese characteristics (Zhu, 2002).

The market economy with Chinese characteristics was not only revealed over the partial privatization of a national industry but also through a series of economic protectionism in the screen industry. The imported quota on foreign films is a representative example. The Chinese film industry officially entered the international market in 1994 when the Film Administrative Bureau, under the Ministry of Radio, Film, and Television (MRFT) decided to import 10 foreign movies per year as a revenue-sharing practice to solve the situation of declining in cinema goes and solve the financial crisis of domestic studios. However, 70 percent of China's film market was quickly captured by American films. The trend of Hollywood movies' dominance lasted from 1994 to 2004. Debates about the effectiveness of the import quota have risen. The quota steadily increased, from 10 to 20 and to 34 in 2002. However, in 2004 when Chinese films enjoyed its first success in taking over 50 percent of the market share, the industry has experienced non-stop development. And yet, along with the import quota, China still has never stopped using its cultural protectionism policy since. This is paradoxical which shows that China's case is an oddity among the argument in the ineffectiveness of protectionism in cultural products trade, which was mentioned above. Under pressure to 'play fair' on the field of global media, China has maintained its own strategies. Under the circumstances, this study conducts an analysis of Chinese film development from 1995 to 2017 to argue that the protection policies that have been brought to Chinese national cinema in the era of the market-oriented economy have helped to develop the film industry. By examining the development of the Chinese film industry, the thesis not only can

evaluate the effects of cultural protectionisms in the industry but also can examine market factors that contribute to the success of the industry.

Not many studies conducted about the success of the Chinese film industry that has been affected by both market and non-market factors. Neither the papers that research the elements lead to the success of the industry under the protectionism. Rather, many studies concentrate on the correspondence or the inter-influence between Hollywood and China film market. The paper “Cultural Policy and Film Industry as Negotiation of Power: the Chinese State’s Role and Strategies in its Engagement with Global Hollywood 1994-2012” by Wendy Su took a similar perspective (Su, 2014). The author took an approach on the global-local interplay to explore the flexibility of the Chinese state in playing two forces at the same time: a ruling force and a market force. Some studies mainly focus on the effect of globalization on the Chinese film industry, which includes analyzing the opportunities and challenges of the market. The typical studies are Emilie Yueh-yu Yeh and Darrell William Davis, Re-nationalizing China’s film industry: case study on the China Film Group and film marketization (Yeh & Davis, 2008). Li Huiqun with the paper “Opportunities and challenges of globalization for the Chinese film industry” analyzes the strengths and weaknesses of the Chinese film industry and proposes opportunities and challenges for the field in the globalization era, specifically under the influence of Hollywood (Li, 2010). Other studies would prefer censorship topics, some specific successful movies or the political purpose of the government. In 2014, Hongmei Yu in the article From Kundun to Mulan: A Political-Economic Case Study of Disney and China argues that mutual economic interests have become a crucial incentive for both to resolve, or at least downplay, political differences (Yu, 2014).

The paper argues that in the globalization era, the protectionist policy in the case of China has helped to develop the film industry and it is worthy to mention the contribution of market factors in the field as the same time. The research question of the thesis is: What are the elements that help the Chinese film industry in achieving its success? To answer the question, there are three sub research questions that the paper would study in each chapter of the paper. Did the protectionist policy helps to develop the Chinese film industry under the influence of Hollywood movies? What are the characters of Chinese blockbusters? What are the contributions of the market’s factors according to Litman’s model that help the Chinese film market share surpass Hollywood movies?

(Following is the part of second sub research question)

Chinese blockbusters with Hollywood characteristics

In globalization and commercialization process, the Chinese movies market has changed and adapted some standards of Hollywood industry from aesthetic model for commercial mainstream entertainment filmmaking to the models of production, promotion, and distribution, the rise of a Hollywood-style star and more. In this way, the new concept “Chinese blockbuster with Hollywood characteristics” has emerged. Hollywood blockbusters are model as “large-scale promotional campaigns, widespread controversies, product and promotional tie-ins, and action figures, along with countless spin-offs and knockoffs” (Berry, 2013).

The movie “Hero” (2002) by Zhang Yi Mou was the first Chinese blockbuster that followed Hollywood style and succeeded. The film broke all existing Chinese box-office records at that time with 248 million RMB of box office revenue (Top 10, 2019). Typical Hollywood characteristics that were used and contributed in the success of the movie are action figure, high technology, product and promotional tie-ins and large-scale promotional campaigns. A number of actors and actresses were casted not only from mainland (Zhang Ziyi and Chen Daoming), but also from Hong Kong (Maggie Cheung and Tony Leung) and even from the United States (Donnie Yen). High-budget for promotion. The film combined stunning cinematography with incredible martial-arts sequences and inspired special effects, which barely new to both Chinese movie makers and domestic audience. A crucial factor that achieved the success of the movie was the large scale promotional campaign. Private jets were used to shuttle the cast around China on a whirlwind set of screenings. Press conferences and interviews were held to promote the film (Berry, 2013). An amount of 15 million RMB was spent for promotion the movie during the time of only 10000 RMB was spent each movie in the publicity (Aranburu, 2017).

The movie as the industry has developed rapidly has been surpassed several times subsequently. However, it cemented a formula for this Chinese blockbuster with Hollywood characteristics. Since, Chinese movie producers have been caring more about promotion budget and plan which had never been too important for them before. The format then was followed by an A-list filmmakers such as Chen Kaige’s *The Promise* (2005) and Feng Xiaogang’s *The Banquet* (夜宴, 2006), together with Zhang’s own *House of Flying Daggers* (2004) and the *Curse of the*

Golden Flower (2006). The success of those movies in following years lied on producer makers who were the Fifth-generation filmmakers in China. According to Zhang Yi Mou, China has countless younger and experimental directors who can make good small, personal films but only a handful of name-brand directors are able to attract the funding that enough to produce big-budget films (Berry, 2013).

The movie “the Wolf Warrior 2”

Since 2002, Chinese blockbuster appeared frequently with increasing number by years. The definition of Chinese blockbuster by box office revenue also has been changing due to the development of the market. According to the Chinese market, a blockbuster is defined as is a film that earns exceeding 100 million RMB. In 2017, the concept of Chinese blockbuster was redefined. A blockbuster is a film that is screened for at least 5 weeks and earns exceeding 1billion RMB (Chinese Film Publication, 2018). The movie “the Wolf Warrior 2” was the incredible Chinese blockbuster that pushed this changing. The movie with a military-action theme broke a Chinese record of the highest-grossing Chinese movie of all time by earning 5.67 billion at the box office (Chinese Film Publication, 2018). The movie as preceded Chinese blockbusters that have been impressing the audience with Hollywood-standard action scenes and visual effects. However, its exploitation of patriotism was the turning point of the movie that attracted a huge number of moviegoers.

Patriotism has been a popular topic for Chinese cinema since 1980s. However, the topic would have not raised again until the speech of President Xi Jinping at the recent Chinese Communist Party’s 19th Party Congress. “We have achieved great progress in the construction of ideology and culture” ... “The main theme is louder, the positive energy is stronger, and the confidence in our culture is reinforced!” (Chinahandsmag, 2015). The claim of President Xi revealed the plan of the Chinese Communist Party in promoting its political agenda in arts and culture. The theme of patriotism has infused through Chinese movies and TV shows and the way how the audience accepted has showed the successful of the plan and the powerful of President Xi’s speech.

By analyzing the content of the movie, patriotism as well as Hollywood characteristics were revealed. The movie is set in an African country with an Ebola-like epidemic. The hero of

the movie is a Chinese soldier named Leng Feng. He is a military guy and he treats everyone equally. He fiercely fights with local militant groups while protecting medical workers and fellow Chinese civilians. The high spot of the movie happens when the movie's female lead, a UN doctor named Rachel, calls the U.S. embassy for help, but the call does not go through. And then the Chinese military entered. The Chinese warship comes to rescue people who trapped in the chaos. The patriotism appears as a climax when the Chinese passport comes into sight with a bold statement on the screen: "To the citizens of People's Republic of China: when you encounter dangers oversea, do not give up! Please remember, you have a strong nation that has your back." In the real Chinese passport, there is no such a statement like that. However, in *Wolf Warrior II*, the audience enjoyed the strength of China and its capacity for overseas crisis management. Libya crisis could be the existent example that back up the story of the movie. In 2011, during the Libya civil war, China evacuated about 36,000 of its nationals out of the country in around 10 days. (Mu, 2011).

By highlighting a Chinese hero to the world, *Wolf Warrior II* was criticized as propaganda movie with a state-produced political idea. However, the movie is a commercial movie in fact. First, the producer of the movie is Wu Jing, a martial art star and the main action of the movie as well. The movie isn't the product of one of China's mega-studios, such as Huayi, Bona, Enlight or China Film Group. Rather, it was conceived and controlled by Beijing Century and by Wu, who started planning a sequel immediately after the first film. He also teamed up with Hollywood directors like the Russo brothers (*Captain America: The Winter Soldier*) as advisers. Second, the movie was invested by totally 21 investors (leaded by Beijing Jetsen Technology, Beijing Jingxi Culture & Tourism, Beijing Enlight Media, Wanda Film Holding,...) with the amount of money as 30 million USD.

According to professors in the field, the movie basically is a hero movie that no different from a Western or a Jackie Chan or Jet Li martial arts movie (Frater, 2017). The movie as expected enjoys Chinese audiences by combining the best elements of action and international stars, which is a familiar Hollywood style in Chinese blockbusters. However, the success of patriotism in the movie is unexpected.

Back to the day of the Mao era, “main theme” was referred for state ideology films. During the years, the “main theme” films were mainly concentrated on the heroics of exemplary party members, the biographies of party leaders or historical events with political messages, and were often required as study material in schools and state institutions. Typical films were as *The Birth of New China* (1989), *Jiao Yulu* (1990), and *Zhou Enlai* (1991). The remarkable popularity of patriotic movies like *Wolf Warrior II* announces a new successful transformation of Chinese “main theme” movies from propaganda materials to commercial productions.

Conclusion

“Chinese blockbusters with Hollywood characteristics” within the Chinese film community have already transformed moviemaking practices and the very nature of the industry. The industry is getting used to a Chinese movie with international element: invested by foreign studios, directed by foreign directors, shot in China and starred a transnational cast. Just as it is comparatively common for a typical Hollywood film to be directed by a British director, star an Australian lead, and be shot on location in Canada. This transformation, de-territorialization of the Chinese cinema shows a certain influence of Hollywood as the commercial Chinese film industry is opening up. Chinese blockbusters are practicing Hollywood characteristics in its filmmaking. However, it does not reduce the Chinese in Chinese cinema in its territorial, linguistic, and cultural components. “*Wolf Warrior 2*” with the raising of patriotism is a strong evidence. After 20 years, it is time for audiences and critics to engage with the complexity strangeness of this new reality.

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Dedication

Part of Thesis.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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